
DECEMBER 2019

MID-TERM EVALUATION REPORT

SOLAR ENERGY FOR A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

Deliverable D5.1
Mid-term Evaluation Report

WP5. Management

Lead Beneficiary: UL – Leiden University

Delivery date: 31 October 2019

Dissemination level: Public

Version: v1.0

This Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 81633

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	816336
Acronym	SUNRISE
Start date of project (Duration)	01/03/2019 (12 months)
Document due date	31/08/2019
Submission date	
Authors	M2i (third-linked party to UL)
Deliverable number	5.1
Deliverable name	Mid-term Evaluation Report
WP	5 – Management

Version	Date	Author	Description
V 0.1	31/10/2019	Iulia Degeratu (M2i)	Drafting first version
V 0.2	1/11/2019	Huub de Groot (UL)	Revision and inclusion MI follow-up review and recommendations
V 0.3	12/11/2019	Iulia Degeratu (M2i)	Revision
V 0.4	13/11/2019	Huub de Groot (UL) Hervé Bercegol (CEA)	Revision and suggestions for reshuffling
V 0.5	29/11/2019	Quality and Impact Assurance team	Comments to sharpen the focus on the SUNRISE review
V 0.6	6/12/2019	Iulia Degeratu (M2i)	Final revision

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Executive Summary

This document, D5.1 Mid-term Evaluation Report, is a deliverable of the SUNRISE Project, which is funded by the European Union's H2020 Programme under Grant Agreement No. 816336.

Members of the Scientific Advisory Board were invited by the SUNRISE consortium to review the work produced within the first six months of operation, materialised in several deliverables, with a focus on the SUNRISE Roadmap, defining the research needs for the development of solar-based products on short, medium and long term. The mid-term evaluation had two components: a remote, written evaluation and an in-depth discussion with the SUNRISE consortium during the SUNRISE Consortium meeting organised in Brussels on 9-11 October 2019. The discussion was documented, and the outputs presented further in this document.

The following main recommendations resulted from the mid-term review sessions on the 9th October and the joint Roadmapping session with Mission Innovation MI IC5 on the following day:

- Enhance the cohesion between the three technology approaches, which is currently less obvious in the roadmap.
- (for Approach 1) Consider other primary energy sources, apart from solar power
- Inform the policy makers at an early stage that SUNRISE *can* in 10 years deliver the technology for direct conversion of solar energy to fuels and chemicals.
- Give sufficient attention to the economic impact, and ensure the technology proposed is affordable for the end-user by developing high efficiency PEC
- To differentiate among various technology platforms in the European landscape, SUNRISE should emphasise the highly novel aspect of the Direct Atmospheric Carbon Capture (DACC) technology.
- Relative to the more established methods in approach 1, where the principle hurdle is CAPEX, stress the importance of breakthroughs in PEC for high efficiency and Biological/biohybrid for diverse products
- Continue the dialogue with Energy-X, essential in order to cover the entire technology readiness spectrum and develop disruptive technologies from concepts to full scale in a very challenging timeframe.

The parallel sessions during the joint event with Mission Innovation IC5 led to very specific feedback, which is listed in the Annexes 5-7 and will be incorporated in the final version of the SUNRISE Roadmap. Since the roadmap is globally competitive, it is recommended that the consortium participates with its roadmap in global agenda setting and policy making.

The recommendations resulted from the mid-term review are also summarised in section 3. The overall conclusion was that SUNRISE has pioneered the transition towards a new energy system, based on abundant raw materials and solar energy as the sole energy source.

To ensure the success of the future large-scale research initiative and address the entire TRL spectrum, the SUNRISE consortium was strongly encouraged to continue collaboration with Energy-X and involve at an early stage political and industrial stakeholders.

1. The mid-term evaluation process

The following members of the SUNRISE Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) were invited by the SUNRISE consortium to review the SUNRISE deliverables:

- Prof. Harry Atwater (Caltech);
- Prof. Walter Leitner (Max-Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion);

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- Prof. Geert-Jan Kramer (Utrecht University);
- Dr. Gaël Giraud (Agence française de développement);
- Prof. Roberta Croce (Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam); and
- Prof. Jean-Pierre Sauvage, Nobel Prize Laureate for Chemistry in 2016.

The former three agreed to contribute remotely to the mid-term evaluation, whereas the latter three had to decline due to prior commitments or health issues. In addition, Prof. Daniel Nocera (Harvard) reviewed the consolidated vision in June, at the occasion of the Stakeholders Workshop.

The documentation was provided on the shared workspace (Plaza) hosted by M2i, and included:

1. SUNRISE deliverables:

- SUNRISE Consolidated vision (deliverable D1.1);
- Roadmap (Deliverable D1.2), accompanied by its technical appendix;
- Innovation process (Deliverable 2.1);
- Dissemination plan (Deliverable 3.1);
- Data management plan (Deliverable 3.4, draft);
- First outline for governance, in the form of a Joint Partnership Proposal on Fossil-Free Industry, proposed jointly with Energy-X.

2. SUNRISE proposal, as background information against which the deliverables could have been evaluated.

The core document for the mid-term review was the SUNRISE Roadmap, paving the route towards achieving commercial maturity level (TRL 9) for sunlight-based fuels and chemicals and at least demonstration level (TRL 7) for CO₂ removal, via three technological approaches:

1. Electrochemical conversion using renewables as energy source,
2. Direct photoelectrochemical conversion – and
3. Direct conversion via biological and biohybrid systems.

The selected SAB members were asked to provide a **written evaluation of the SUNRISE deliverables**, with a focus on the SUNRISE Roadmap. The evaluation should be provided as a two-page document with a structure of choice, before or during the mid-term evaluation sessions in Brussels, on the 9th and 10th of October.

Following the evaluation by the SUNRISE SAB members, on the 11th October, the Roadmap was debated with the experts of the Mission Innovation IC5 “Converting sunlight”, listed as follows:

- Julius Scholz, NOW-GmbH;
- Peter Vach, German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy;
- Winifred Leibl, Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives;
- Pau Farras, National University of Ireland Galway;
- Mehdi Jafarian, University of Adelaide;
- Roel van de Krol, The Helmholtz Association of German Research Centres;
- Philippe Schild, European Commission;
- Nigel Taylor, European Commission/ Joint Research Center.

2. Mid-term evaluation meeting: inputs and discussion

The mid-term evaluation meeting was organised in the frame of the SUNRISE Consortium meeting. The event was scheduled over three days, starting on the 9th October at noon and ending on the 11th October at noon, at EERA in Brussels, 72 rue de Namur. Remote web-based sessions were organised with Prof. W. Leitner on the 9th of October and with Prof. Geert-Jan Kramer on the 10th of October.

Prof. Harry Atwater declined participation to a remote session, nevertheless had discussed during a prior meeting with Prof. A. Vlcek (Heyrovsky Institute, member of the SUNRISE consortium) the status and perspectives of SUNRISE. A brief account is presented further below, along with the other relevant sections of the event minutes.

Furthermore, another SAB member, Prof. Daniel Nocera, discussed his findings during a working dinner on June 18th, following the Stakeholders Workshop (“ramp-up meeting”). Prof. Nocera recommended to engage with private partners to concentrate on the long-term impact, as the private sector can only justify participation in low TRL research when the expected long-term impact is high. In particular, he suggested to keep a sharp focus on the business opportunities, as stated in the proposal:

- Targeting 10% of global crude oil and gas production, the total of which represents a value of €250 billion per annum in the upstream sector, even at the current low-price level;
- Targeting 10% of global investment costs in traditional refineries for upgrading existing plants and building new ones that transform SUNRISE products into certified fuels amounts to an estimated €17 billion per annum for Europe, based on a 10% reinvestment rate per year.

Day-1: Wednesday, October 9th

Opening words by Huub de Groot (LU, coordinator SUNRISE CSA).

The SUNRISE coordinator Huub de Groot (UL) presents briefly the status of the SUNRISE deliverables. The following deliverables have been produced and submitted: *D1.1 Consolidated vision*, *D2.1 Innovation process*, *D3.1 Dissemination plan*. Three other pending deliverables (*D1.2 Roadmap*, *D2.2 Innovation structure* and *D3.2 Data management plan*) are currently being drafted, the Roadmap and the Data management plan having in the meantime been finalised.

Midterm review – session 1

Debrief Mid-term review

Huub de Groot informs the consortium that several members of our Scientific Advisory Board were contacted to perform a mid-term review of the SUNRISE deliverables, primarily the Roadmap. Three members of the SAB reacted positively to this invitation: Prof. Walter Leitner (Max Planck Institute), Prof. Geert Jan Kramer (Copernicus Institute, Utrecht University) and Prof. Harry Atwater (Caltech/JCAP) but eventually only the former two could participate during live, remote sessions. Harry Atwater had a discussion with Prof. A. Vlcek (Heyrovsky) in the US, who also gave a short account via email:

“Harry Atwater was interested in the latest status of SUNRISE, merger with ENERGY-X, etc. I made it clear that, while the merger is going on, the two CSAs are separate and will follow their respective plans until March. Interestingly, he told me that the US Senate agreed that DoE will fund largely fundamental research in solar fuels by 20M USD per year for a period of five years. The emphasis will be on liquid solar fuels, that is CO₂ to methanol, ethanol, propanol, possibly dimethylether, liquid hydrocarbons and N₂ to liquid ammonia. DoE stresses direct conversion (photoelectrochemistry), saying that the science behind electrocatalytic conversion (like ENERGY-X) is largely known. Long-term stability of materials (photoelectrodes) and dual-function materials (a photoelectrode that would also have catalytic activity) are stressed as priority topics. Other aspects of direct conversion (“soft” bioinspired and biohybrid) systems are considered as well.

This new DoE funding will be awarded based on an open competition. Caltech will compete, as a possible continuation of JCAP, which will finish in September 2020. If they get it, they would be interested in collaborating with us.”

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Two skype sessions were planned in the afternoon and the morning of the next day, respectively. At the beginning of the review session, Huub de Groot proposed several questions to guide the discussion with the external reviewers:

- Is there a risk that “the level goes down”, as this is a risk related to any emerging funding opportunity?
- Considering the limited availability of the few experts on artificial photosynthesis for roadmapping processes, is there a risk that “non-experts take the lead”?
- “White spots”, such as for example insufficiently covered priority research directions (e.g. direct conversion of CO₂) or *ex-ante* impact evaluation.

After this introduction, the SUNRISE WP leaders gave individual presentations on the status of their respective work packages.

Summary of WP status by WP leaders

WP 1 Strategy and Structuring: Nicola Armaroli (CNR)

The first major deliverable, “SUNRISE Consolidated vision”, was an extension of the vision from the proposal. The work was initiated by CNR (Dr. Nicola Armaroli and Dr. Andrea Barbieri) and further developed by CEA (Dr. Hervé Bercegol and Dr. Vincent Artero). The next step was to develop the SUNRISE Roadmap, which has the solar-driven circular economy as target for mid-century, with several milestones. The roadmapping required an impressive amount of work, coordinated by Dr. Carina Faber (UCL), whom Nicola thanked on behalf of the consortium.

Q W. Leitner: How did you involve the representatives of large companies (Siemens, Johnson Matthey) – and was that performed at the level of technical people or was the upper level of the hierarchy involved?

A. N. Armaroli: The companies were deeply involved in the discussion and provided important input. A. Huub: When working with companies, it is important to have a deeply committed individual inside the company, a so-called champion – not necessarily from the upper management. We have identified such champions in Engie and Siemens, hence we selected them for the proposal. We also have many industrial supporters.

WP 2 Innovation and exploitation: Arne Roth (Fraunhofer)

The first deliverable, SUNRISE Innovation Process (SIP), introduced the concept of the “SUNRISE valleys”, i.e. “collaborative forums for all partners and stakeholders to meet and set priorities for addressing short-, medium- and long-term challenges for transitioning to a circular economy”.

A first Innovation workshop was organized during the Stakeholders Workshop (Brussels, 17-18 June), which led to the identification of the following steps for an innovation process:

1. Trend analysis: high-level targets, drivers and societal needs; create & analyse scenarios;
2. Idea generation: ways to generate interesting ideas; some stakeholders expressed concerns regarding the protection of IP;
3. Idea evaluation: system-level performance assessment; evaluation of the economic potential; advisory committees and/or external evaluation;
4. Experimentation: use of computational tools, suitable funding, market potential and social acceptance;
5. Commercialization: regulatory issues; compliance with standards – potentially blocking innovation.

Arne presented a SWOT analysis of the SUNRISE Valleys concept. The following weaknesses were mentioned: exclusive (“what about the rest?”); imbalance (too many scientists); internal competition; lack of impact on policymaking due to limited geographical scope. As threats: lack of financial/political support, unstable legislative situation, lack of social acceptance (“not in my backyard” attitude). The upcoming deliverable is the development of the S2S and S2B exploitation plans (due by Month 6, still pending, responsible CEA & JM). Arne suggests the creation of an Innovation team to complete this work. The team would mainly involve the partners involved in WP 2.

Q Leif Hammarström (UU): there was a comment on the lack of a clear path towards the SUNRISE Valleys, the plan towards creating them still needs to be worked out.

Comment W. Leitner: The SUNRISE roadmap aims at TRL 9 in 10 years, this definitely requires industry support and industry needs should be involved early-on. It seems that Energy-X plans to involve industry at a later stage. Industry support does not seem to be fully aligned in both initiatives. The industry needs to plan the implementation justifying the research. Organizing funding commitment for the next 10 years is a challenge. Politicians will need to be convinced that industry commits itself to bring the technology to market. Reaction C. Faber (UCL): TRL 9 comes from the industry partners. Our industry partners (Engie, Siemens) are confident they can reach it within 10 years. Comment Huub: even at TRL 9, there is still innovation/optimization to be performed.

W. Leitner: Your industrial partners are not necessarily experienced in the production processes for the envisaged chemicals (e.g. ammonia synthesis). Reaction L. Baraton (Engie): yes, but we are building this knowledge, Engie has recently invested in expertise on Haber-Bosch and started a pilot project in Australia. There is industrial commitment to go fast towards TRL 9. Reaction E. Simon (Siemens): Indeed, Siemens is not ammonia producer, but we are interested in the conversion of solar energy (production of electrolysers). We are exchanging with specialized partners along the value chain and agree these partners are very important.

W. Leitner: it is important define the products (“X”) you are targeting, and use their specifications for a specific market to drive the innovation. For this, it is crucial to involve end-users, otherwise the science cannot make it to the market. Other demonstrators can be considered, even without subsidies, for example local production of formic acid (from CO₂ and H₂) locally, at small scale – “the lighthouse project”, as proposed in the written review – action Arne Roth to explore this idea.

W. Leitner also recommends to pursue the original idea of the jet fuels, building on the momentum of pressing regulatory demands for aviation. European air carriers (e.g. Lufthansa) are under pressure to reduce emissions and to introduce significant shares of renewable jet fuel. A. Roth (Fraunhofer) indicates that the Aviation Initiative for Renewable Energy in Germany (aireg) aims at reaching a share of 10% renewable jet fuel in the Germany jet fuel mix by 2025¹. Arne comments such a target is unrealistic, since only bio jet fuel is presently available as sustainable fuel alternative for aviation. Such public commitments will most probably trigger a fast development of alternative fuels. Several airports (Dusseldorf, Amsterdam Schiphol and Rotterdam) expressed interest in getting involved in pilot projects for alternative fuels. W. Leitner advises to pursue the idea of an airport demonstrator originally proposed in Energy-X. Action: discuss it with J. Nørskov or B. Weckhuysen (action Huub).

WP 3 Dissemination, communication and education: Laura Lopez (ICIQ)

Dr. Laura Lopez (ICIQ) presents the results of the dissemination tools created and deployed so far. There has been a massive dissemination effort in the scientific community, supported by the partners at national levels. From now onwards, the strategy will slightly shift towards reaching the public and the policy makers. Its goals were presented as follows:

- Strengthen the SUNRISE community
Actions: continue and improve running actions with stakeholders; release video interviews with partners (a first one already launched, with Nicola Armaroli, on circular economy); sharing publication highlights from partners on the blog, increase online presence through contests, events etc.
- Increase involvement of policymakers and citizens
Actions: social media campaigns, features in general media (on roadmap and manifesto), national stakeholders meetings, facts&figures infographics, translation of official video in several EU languages.
- Inclusive plan to reach younger generation
Actions: visits to schools/ universities etc.

¹ <https://aireg.de/en/topics/current-projects/the-goals-of-aireg-until-2025/>

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- Joint communication actions with Energy-X

Laura Lopez also presented a web statistic, showing good outreach: the SUNRISE community now counts 1.650 members.

Comment W. Leitner: The general public can be very difficult to address without a concrete output that they are able to judge.

WP 4 Governance: Frédéric Chandezon (CEA)

A public debate was organized with representatives from EU and national governments on the 17th June at the Stakeholders Workshop in Brussels. The key take-away messages were:

- Join efforts with ENERGY-X (in the meantime materialised in a joint initiative prospectively named SUN-ERGY);
- Build visibility through a SUNRISE brand, with wide dissemination;
- Involve associate NGOs and general public;
- Involve industry right from the start and clarify the IP management;
- Activate member states and national communities. There were national SUNRISE events, organized in Italy, Poland, Switzerland, France. SUNRISE was also presented in third- and associated countries, during events in South Africa and Turkey (as per information from Artur Braun, EMPA). Upcoming national events: Netherlands, November 6th; Finland, December 8th.

Status of the SUN-ERGY initiative:

The two consortia (SUNRISE and Energy-X) put forward a Joint Partnership Proposal “3FCM: Fossil Free Fuels, Chemicals and Materials for a circular economy”. The outcome of the previous consultations held at the EC level was that no room is left for a new partnership in the 2021 round, leaving the following alternatives:

- 1. Join existing partnerships: this option was discussed during the first SUN-ERGY board meeting in Aachen on 20 August. Both consortia (SUNRISE and Energy-X) agreed that joining the existing programmes would lead to fragmentation of R&I efforts and therefore, this option was dismissed.*
- 2. Promote a single initiative during the second round of call for partnerships (2024) – the option agreed by all. There are co-programmed, co-funded and institutionalised partnerships. SUNRISE is considering the latter two options, with a preference for institutionalised partnerships.*

WP 5 Management (CSA): Huub de Groot (UL)

The coordinator Huub de Groot states that the consortium is now in a “living strategy” mode. The final and critical step is “bridging into action”. In this context, it is important that representatives of both consortia submit proposals to the relevant, currently open calls organised by the EC, such as the FET Proactive call “Emerging paradigms and communities” (FETPROACT-EIC-05-2019), closing on the 13th November. Joint teams SUNRISE/Energy-X should be setup to organise proposals for such calls, to show the interest of the community. The next steps for “bridging into action”:

- Comprehensive description of the future plan (blueprint of a large-scale research initiative), with a manifesto covering the six documents;
- Mission Innovation connects to the Blueprint;
- Governance connects to Energy-X;
- Develop a joint innovation plan, to cover the full spectrum of technology readiness, from TRL 0 to TRL 9.

A final event (symposium) should be organised in February 2020, across a few days, and include a working session, as well as a larger event for the SUNRISE community, at a prestigious location.

Midterm review – session 2 with Walter Leitner

Prof. Walter Leitner congratulated the consortium for the work delivered in such a short period of time. The Roadmap requires further work, based on further discussion with Energy-X. With regard to the roadmap content, it is important to couple “Power-to-X” to the needs of each sector, whereby the challenges are very different: Electricity, 2018: 647 TWh (38% renewable), Mobility & Transport, 2017: 663TWh (5% renewables); Chemical industry, 2016: 20 Mt raw materials (13% renewables). For aviation, only hydrocarbons can be considered (Fischer-Tropsch) – see [Annex 1](#) and [Annex 2](#).

For the future large-scale initiative, it is important to engage the society and gain its acceptance at an early stage. This is crucial not so much for the scientific developments, but for the upscaling and implementation:

Q. H. Bercegol: One of the arguments in the roadmap is to increase the efficiency of converting the solar input, which translates into a productivity increase per unit of land area and unit of time. How can we integrate other sources (different from direct solar) in the productivity indicator?

W. Leitner: we need to identify the areas where we have sufficient solar influx and for a sufficiently long period of time - this is the case for any conversion process. Hybrid/combined solutions should also be considered (and actually are, to a certain extent) in the roadmap.

Comment N. Armaroli: we need renewable electricity in each country, based on the sources that are available in those particular countries. Our deployment targets in 10 years (1.000 ha) are an extremely bold claim, considering we start from very small devices. PV took decades to progress from cm to m. Even if we are now in a different technology area – scaling up to the scale we promised is still a very hard challenge.

Q. W. Leitner: do you aim at large scale or decentralised operations? Or both? Huub: We will scale up operations gradually: in 10 years we want to demonstrate that it is possible to fly a plane. And achieve 80% of circularity for the target molecules.

Q. Hervé: You were not convinced about DAC (Direct Air Capture & Conversion of CO₂) and its link with rest of the project. Carbon capture activity was integrated later in the proposal in a system view of CCUS and due to the important energy loss encountered in DAC (Direct Air Capture of CO₂). Then it appeared that a major gain could come from the merging of the two steps: capture and conversion. Is your analysis different? A. W. Leitner: You have three major technology approaches, centred around conversion, and carbon capture seemed as a separate point, not influenced by/coming out of the other approaches. Hervé: DAC has not been optimised yet, as it has only been developed to provide CO₂ gas for CCS. We need to know in what form (chemical) the product will be it come; indeed, we will need to adapt CC for the technological approaches.

Day-2: Thursday, October 10th

Wrap-up of previous day

H. Bercegol (CEA) gave a brief account of the discussions from the previous day, followed by a discussion in the consortium on how those points are/can be addressed in the roadmap:

H. de Groot (UL): In his written review, W. Leitner also conveyed a very important point, that we should not consider a single renewable energy source (wind). Synergies should be sought, we should think of our position towards wind. S. Baumann (Jülich): There is no conflict between the two approaches, as there will never be too much electricity for the foreseeable time horizon. J. Kargul (Warsaw): the key is in the dichotomy direct and indirect power generation. A. Magnuson (UU): our roadmap refers to renewable electricity and artificial photosynthesis, therefore we do not exclude wind. We can also stress that wind+electrolysis is an available technology, it can be our starting point for a new energy market. H. Bercegol (CEA): We could also emphasise that our approach intends to maximise the photon conversion. E. Simon (Siemens): In some regions there is a lot of wind and not so much sun, the implementation routes should then consider the geographical hot spots for each type of renewable. Other comments of W. Leitner referred to centralised vs. decentralised and biomass: we will adopt a decentralised approach and not include biomass in the roadmap.

Midterm review – session 2 – Prof. Geert-Jan Kramer (Utrecht University), see Annex 3.

Prof. Gert Jan Kramer commends the effort of the SUNRISE team to create a roadmap for solar fuels and chemicals, as this is a critical topic for the coming decades. Aware of the intention to merge with Energy-X, he thinks synergy can lead to a stronger impact, allowing to build on the strengths of both communities and remove the existing overlap. However, there seems to be an excessive optimism on the speed of progressing through the TRL towards commercial maturity. About a 100 billion \$ are needed to get to the bottom line of a new energy technology and 1.000 billion \$ for it to achieve “materiality”². It is useful to consider the year 2000 as reference year, as the past two decades are characterised by a fantastic pace of change. Clean tech is now a 300 billion \$ industry, but there is still significantly untapped potential to scale up this market to a trillion \$.

Regarding the shift to market, the estimated affordable cost is 200 \$ per barrel of solar fuel, as shown in a recent paper from Joule³. The SUNRISE roadmap targets the production of fuels from solar energy alone. The challenge is to realistically estimate the timeline needed to scale up this technology, which is ultimately based on the “artificial leaf” concept. At the same time, there are technologies like electrolysis that are already available for the production of “solar fuels”.

Questions from G. J. Kramer for the SUNRISE consortium:

- 1. Will SUNRISE be developing a new technology platform? Or will you be feeding into existing technology platforms?** Recommendation: the latter, however the roadmap seems to be written as if for the former. This needs to be clarified in order to build the most suitable consortium for a future large-scale research programme on solar fuels. The notable exception is Direct Atmospheric Carbon Capture (DACC), for which a TRL jump from 1-2 to 5-7 in 10 years seems unrealistic in the opinion of G. J. Kramer⁴.

C. Faber (UCL): yes, we will develop a new technology platform, this was the purpose of the flagship initiative. Our approach was inspired from the Quantum technology platform, which also deals with a large spectrum of TRL levels. Reaction G. J. Kramer: You are framing this programme in the landscape of the EU projects, whereas I framed my question from a business perspective. Your intention then relies on the support of the industry to reach the higher TRL levels you are envisioning. There is then a significant risk of overpromising. As technology agnostic, nothing is more frustrating than seeing change around the corner and still not happening. It is important to inform the policy makers that we have the technology to make significant progress in the coming decades. Looking at the numbers from electrolysis section, 1.000 euro/kW is mentioned, but this might not be attractive for industry (which is already at 250 euro/kW). If you are aiming for a completely new technology platform, you need to consider the technology trends and the likely situation in 10 years from now.

H. de Groot (UL): It will be indeed critical to produce solar fuels at an affordable cost (as indicated by our industrial partners). Prof. John Mathews looked at the energy transition from China, which exceeds the most optimistic predictions⁵. Reaction G. J. Kramer: there has been progress on new technologies which in some cases overtook the old ones. However, the price must be affordable.

L. Hammarström (UU): Our roadmap was based on a timeline of 10 years and a funding of 1 billion euro. Perhaps we need to move away from these boundaries and focus on realistic time and budget scales.

- 2. How do you plan to handle within a single programme, technology development at such different TRL levels?**

H. Bercegol (CEA): Should DACC be a new technology platform, and how would you see it developing within SUNRISE? A. G. J. Kramer: I am insufficiently aware of the boundary conditions in the EU funding landscape. However, the DACC is the truly open challenge, where breakthroughs are needed. This only justifies the emergence of a new technology platform, whereas the others can be fed into existing technology platforms.

² G.J. Kramer and M. Haigh, “No quick switch to low-carbon energy”, Nature volume 462, pages 568–569 (2009).

³ Kraan et al., “An Energy Transition That Relies Only on Technology Leads to a Bet on Solar Fuels”, Joule (2019), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2019.07.029>.

⁴ Nevertheless, the Swiss company Climeworks has already reached demonstration level (TRL 6), with several plants already operational. This technology has the potential to reach commercial application within the next 10 years.

⁵ John Mathews, “Global Green Shift: Where Ceres meets Gaia”, 2017.

Reactions industrial representatives: Dr. E. Simon (Siemens): Once the technology reaches efficiency levels comparable with existing ones, it will become an interesting investment. Then, once technology reaches higher TRL, the industry can definitely take over. Dr. L. Baraton (Engie): We can invest in electrolysis to produce hydrogen, and this can kick-start the development of artificial photosynthesis.

3. Which synergies do you see?

H. de Groot (UL): We are committed to merging with Energy-X. SUNRISE is transitioning from an initial club of enthusiasts into an inclusive community, where economic and social sciences are also represented.

Session with Mission Innovation IC5: SUNRISE roadmap review and feedback

The IC5 members were given access to the draft of the Roadmap document, and following a plenary session, the group split up in breakout sessions to prepare recommendations for improving the roadmap.

Carina Faber - Presentation SUNRISE Roadmap (see [Annex 4](#)).

Some background was given on how the SUNRISE Vision and Priority Research Directions have been defined. As a logical next step, the SUNRISE Roadmap will provide a guideline on *how* to reach the Vision goals when starting from the current state.

As a starting point, major milestones have been defined for the three classes of SUNRISE products, i.e. hydrogen, ammonia and carbon-based chemicals & jet fuels. The milestones are defined for 2025 – 2030 – 2050. Secondly, major technological targets related to the major milestones have been defined. A number of Key Enabling Technologies needed to accomplish the milestones have been listed and will need to be further developed within SUNRISE. Further information is found in Carina’s presentation in the appendix.

Next, the group split in three break-out sessions and collect input to revise the milestones and the technical appendices to the draft Roadmap.

Plenary Questions and Feedback

Question Prof. Roel van der Krol (Helmholtz): One of the Roadmap scenarios refers to “less energy use by 2050”, which is unrealistic. Although future process efficiencies will be higher and at the same time people consume less (at least in Europe), you need to avoid the impression that a lower energy consumption is needed to reach the SUNRISE goals. This should be rephrased in the Roadmap. Laura Lopez (ICIQ) answered that the roadmap did not develop scenarios, but that the mentioned scenario stems from the EC's 2050 long-term strategy and that she will add more information about this scenario through a footnote in the roadmap.

Question Dr. Peter Vach (BMBF): When reading the document, one could get the impression that SUNRISE is building an entirely new platform to reach a carbon-free future. Huub de Groot replies that we should indeed be careful how to profile ourselves. This is in line with Geert-Jan Kramer’s remark; “don’t try to cover it all”.

Question Prof. James Durrant (Imperial College): Should we pay more attention to transportation of solar fuels between different global regions, for instance from sunnier to less sunnier areas? Hervé Bercegol replies that this aspect has not been included in the Roadmap because radiation differences are typically not that large, for instance ‘only’ a factor of two between South and North Europe. Huub adds that we should aim at local production in highly efficient economic areas. China has attempted land grabbing in Africa but eventually decided to focus on its own territory. Roel v.d. Krol does not agree. A factor two is a significant difference and therefore transportation of solar fuels should be taken in account. As an example, the EC is currently looking into options for hydrogen production in North-Africa. Huub de Groot (UL) questions if North-African countries are willing to support this. Artur Braun (EMPA) would expect such countries to be happy to get involved. The consortium will further explore opportunities for solar fuel production on other continents. If possible, SUNRISE could make stronger links to existing, smaller, European consortia already working on similar topics. Huub agrees that these groups should be included in further consultations.

Dr. Ann Magnuson (UU) comments that sustainability goals have not been clearly described in the Roadmap (to be reviewed). Dr. Nicola Armaroli (CNR): Overall, it is difficult to get highly accurate numbers on e.g. electrification, hydrogen use, etc. to enable a precise comparison between, for instance, specific regions and the entire globe.

Dr. Peter Vach (BMBF): The 2050 goals in the Roadmap seem to be less ambitious compared with other documents. For instance, if in 2050 a few thousand households will be equipped with SUNRISE technology, politicians will not be impressed. Huub replies that these numbers apply for low TRL technologies developed in Approach 2 and 3. They will be part of the end game, but high TRL technologies described Approach 1 will be deployed on a much larger scale. Peter Vach replies that although we need to be realistic, we do need to communicate very clearly that SUNRISE will contribute to the Energy Transition. The consortium will therefore perform a critical review of target numbers mentioned in the Roadmap.

Breakout sessions followed, on specific chemical targets in SUNRISE roadmap, with the goal to collect 10 concrete recommendations on each topic listed below for revisions of the Roadmap.

1. Hydrogen: short presentation by Prof. Leif Hammarström (UU), see Annex 5.

Discussion: Roel v.d. Krol advises that the goals should be in the triangle Efficiency-Stability-Upscaling. Leif Hammarström agrees that we should describe the goals in these areas. The, goals must be both realistic and ambitious. The Roadmap milestones should be once more reviewed against the SUNRISE Vision. The target price of 4 €/kg might be too high, as others already mention lower prices. Carina Faber (UCL) states this is just a rough estimate. Engie and Siemens agreed to the number, but the range is very broad; a footnote should be added to the Roadmap for clarification. The condition “product stability >1 year” may be confusing and should also be reviewed.

2. Ammonia: short presentation by Dr. Vincent Artero (CEA), see Annex 6.

Discussion: Additional LCA input is needed – action from Stefano Cucurachi (UL)

3. Carbon-based chemicals and (jet) fuels: short presentation by Dr. Hervé Bercegol (CEA), see Annex 7.

Discussion: Need more consistency on units used in the Roadmap; the goals must be expressed in units that are understandable for policy makers and chemical industry.

4. General context, governance, lobbying: short presentation by Dr. Frédéric Chandezon, see Annex 8.

Discussion: The dissemination of the roadmap should be discussed during the next MB meeting (scheduled on November 7th, 2019). By that time, all suggested changes will be implemented, so that the roadmap could be shared with the supporters the following week. Consultations can be done via the website. National “Roadmap dissemination events” need to be organized on short term. The executive summary will be distributed to the EC through Philippe Schild.

3. Conclusions

The overall conclusion was that SUNRISE undertook a very important, pioneering task, with the future challenge of getting industrial and political support to reposition the European economy on a circular trajectory. SUNRISE not only addressed the European level, but through cooperation with the Mission Innovation IC5 “Converting sunlight”, took the initiative to drive global roadmapping efforts for artificial photosynthesis.

The partnership with Energy-X was seen as a crucial step to engage all stakeholders of the solar-to-products community in generating a future large-scale research initiative that would cover the full spectrum of the technology readiness levels.

The support of the industry will be paramount to materialise the transition to a solar-based economy by 2050. The consortium should seek ways to engage with the industry along the entire value chain. At the end of the SUNRISE CSA, the Roadmap will be presented to the EC and will provide input to the Calls in Horizon Europe, as well as lay the foundations of an institutionalized partnership as of 2024. We will need to perform an effective lobbying on both national and European levels, in order to ensure the implementation of the Roadmap by means of funded research projects.

Annexes

- 1. Written evaluation input from Prof. dr. W. Leitner, Max-Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion**
- 2. Presentation for the Mid-term Evaluation session by Prof. dr. W. Leitner, Max-Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion**
- 3. Presentation for the Mid-term Evaluation session by Prof. dr. G.-J. Kramer, Utrecht University**
- 4. Presentation on SUNRISE Roadmap by Dr. C. Faber, Université Catholique de Louvain**
- 5. Short presentation on the Hydrogen section of the Roadmap by Prof. Leif Hammarström, Uppsala University**
- 6. Short presentation on the Ammonia section of the Roadmap by Dr. Vincent Artero, CEA**
- 7. Short presentation on the Carbon-based chemicals and (jet) fuels section of the Roadmap by Dr. Hervé Bercegol, CEA**
- 8. Short presentation on the general context, governance and lobbying by Dr. Frédéric Chandezon, CEA**

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The SUNRISE Consortium

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Mülheim an der Ruhr, der 1. November 2019

Mid-term review;

Dear Ms Degeratu:

With E-Mail from September 13, you have requested an assessment of the activities of the SUNRISE consortium with respect to the deliverables for the mid-term assessment. I am very happy to follow this request as I have been very impressed by the initiative and its development in the recent months. In particular, I will focus my assessment on the Roadmap Document (D1.2), the “Consolidated Vision” (deliverable D1.1), and the first outline for governance, in the form of a Joint Partnership Proposal on Fossil-Free Industry, proposed jointly with Energy-X. I consider these deliverables the central outcome and action plan for the future development of SUNRISE.

With kind regards,

(Prof. Dr. Walter Leitner)

General:

The SUNRISE consortium was formed as a Coordination & Support Action (CSA) to identify research needs and innovation targets to facilitate the transition to a circular economy and a carbon-neutral society. The ultimate goal is a sustainable CO₂ cycle, where the concentration in the atmosphere is decreased and then maintained at a level compatible with climate stability and sustainable use of natural resources and land. Towards this vision, SUNRISE aims at competitive production pathways to hydrogen, ammonia and light carbon-bearing molecules from atmospheric water, nitrogen and carbon dioxide. A major focus lies on technology concepts often referred to as “artificial photosynthesis”. On a short term, this can be achieved by utilization of hydrogen produced from non-fossil resources exploiting renewable energy via photovoltaics and electrochemical processes. On a longer term, the development of photoelectrochemical, biological and biohybrid systems is envisaged in SUNRISE. An associated important strategic development is the transition from a centralized production to a more decentralized approach favouring the development of a circular economy at a local scale. With this approach, SUNRISE aims to contribute to a fully CO₂-free electricity system, a CO₂-neutral circular economy, net climate neutral mobility for people and goods as well as affordable negative emissions technologies at a significant scale.

A major deliverable for the first period was the generation of a SUNRISE Roadmap to define technology options and strategic action points (D1.2) for the “Consolidated Vision” (deliverable D1.1). Furthermore, a first outline for governance, in the form of a Joint Partnership Proposal on Fossil-Free Industry, proposed jointly with Energy-X was also to be delivered. The present assessment will focus on these three deliverables as they represent the core for all other actions and milestones of the CSA.

Consolidated Vision:

The consolidated vision reflected in the Executive Summary of the Roadmap and highlighted above has been derived from consultations with various stakeholders and intensive internal discussions. It provides a bold and ambitious target of crucial importance to a sustainable future in Europe. It is highly appreciated that science and innovation are clearly aimed at the three dimensions of sustainability, ecological welfare, economic benefits, and societal needs. To engage the scientific community, industrial stakeholders, and NGOs in this process arriving at a common vision is a major achievement.

Roadmap:

In the draft of the Roadmap, the overarching goals are translated into “technological approaches”, “technology milestones”. For the latter, “technology targets” are discussed in detail. Again, the input of the scientific community was gathered extensively through consultation and workshops. In particular, this comprises the SUNRISE stakeholder event with more than 170 participants held June 17.-18 2019 at Brussels. This was followed by a three days (17.-19. July 2019) roadmapping workshop of the project team in the EERA premises in Brussels. The results of these workshops, as outlined in detail in the Roadmap and the Technical Annex, were discussed intensively with the Energy-X consortium, and the initiatives jointly engaged in an open forum at the EuropaCat conference in August in Aachen, attracting some 350 participants.

In its draft version of September 2019, the SUNRISE Roadmap has identified three major technological approaches (TA) defined as:

- TA-1: Electrochemical conversion with solar power
- TA-2: Direct conversion via photoelectrochemical cells
- TA-3: Direct conversion via biological and biohybrid systems

An increasing level of integration between energy harvest and (bio-)chemical conversion is inherent in this list. For the energy harvest, direct use of sunlight, largely via photovoltaics and related technologies is envisaged, inspired by the concept of “artificial photosynthesis”.

Based on this concept, “technology milestones (TM)” are defined that translate roughly into the potential for implementation of the three approaches in specifically targeted applications.

These milestones are:

- TM-1: Sustainable hydrogen production
- TM-2: Sustainable ammonia production
- TM-3: Sustainable carbon capture
- TM-4: Sustainable production of commodity chemicals and (jet) fuels
- TM-5: Long-lasting carbon-based materials

Each “technology milestone” is broken down further into “technology targets”, for which timelines, technology readiness level (TRL, current and target), and action points for research and development are presented.

The five “technology milestones” are clearly addressing major challenges and crucial pillars to reach the SUNRISE vision. They are central elements in the transition towards a defossilized industrial future. The direct connection to the three major “technological approaches” remains at this stage somewhat less obvious, however. In particular TM-3 “Sustainable carbon capture” will not be influenced significantly by progress in the three TAs.

Furthermore, the upfront definition of photovoltaics as the direct exploitation of sunlight inherently defines concrete system boundaries for the implementation strategies in the TM applications. While this may well be necessary to provide a common framework within the consortium actions, it needs to be assessed more clearly on a systems level. This seems in particular relevant in view of the goal to provide decentralised, regional solutions. While direct use of sunlight may be the preferred option in parts of Europe that have major influx

form direct solar power, other parts that are rich in wind, geothermal or even bio-based energy sources may benefit more from other technologies to harvest the primary energy. It is currently not yet obvious from the roadmap, whether SUNRISE proposes the approach to utilize photovoltaics as ultimate and single entry point universally or under a defined set of boundary conditions.

Joint Partnership Proposal on Fossil-Free Industry:

The documents for the mid-term review contain also an outline for a partnership with the working title “**Fossil Free Industry: Fossil-free Fuels, Chemicals and Materials for a Circular Economy**”. The concept results from the intensive interaction between the two CSAs “SUNRISE” and “ENERGY-X”. Both initiatives share the common goal to provide technological solutions for the *grand challenges* originating from the re-design of the energy/chemistry-nexus and thus turn them into *major opportunities* for European societies.

The consolidated vision of SUNRISE is reflected perfectly in the short description of the proposed partnership. While there are of course differences between the technological approaches and detailed technology targets between the two CSAs, they are complementary and in many ways synergistic, rather than competing. With the urgent need to develop disruptive technologies from concepts to full scale in a very challenging short timeframe, the joint discussion is therefore evaluated extremely positive.

Among the achievements of both CSAs in the initial phase, three main aspects are particularly impressive: mobilisation of scientific creativity, participation of global industrial players along the value chains, and engagement of societal stakeholders through NGOs. The SUNRISE consortium is strongly encouraged to continue in direction of the joint partnership.

SUNRISE Midterm Review

Walter Leitner

Video Conference
October 10, 2019

The "Fossil Age"

Closing the Carbon Cycle

Power-To-X and Sector Coupling

“Power-to-X”: The Challenges

Electrolysis

L.G.J. de Haart, R.-A. Eichel, et al. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2017**, 56, 5402–5406.

Catalysis

J. Klankermayer, W. Leitner, et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2016**, 55, 7296–7343.

A. Bardow, W. Leitner, et al., *Chem. Rev.* **2018**, 118, 434–504.

„Energiewende“ oder „Stromwende“?

- **Electricity, 2018:**
647 TWh @ 38% renewable ¹
- **Mobility & Transport, 2017:**
663 TWh @ 5% renewable ²
- **Chemical Industry, 2016:**
20 Mio t raw materials @ 13% renewable ³

Electricity from Renewables

Mobility with Renewables

„Import“ of Energy will remain essential for the Mobility Sector

„Überschussstrom“

Fluctuating Supply and Demand

25 TWh (2030)
→ ca. 1 Mio t fuel

„Sweet Spots“

alpha ventus
North Sea (near Borkum)

0,24 TWh (60 MW rated capacity)
→ ca. 10.000 t fuel

Topaz Solar Farm
California/USA

1 TWh (550 MW rated capacity)
→ ca. 40.000 t fuel

Some data for Germany

Figure 2. Distribution of CO₂ point sources (>0.1 Mt a⁻¹) in 2011 in a) Europe and b) Germany as exemplary country. The CO₂ emissions map has been created using the PowerMap Preview Plugin for Microsoft Excel 2013.⁵⁹ Color online.

Challenges and opportunities for sector coupling

- ⇒ **Dynamic deployment of cost-effective renewable electricity, but energy will remain a valuable resource**
- ⇒ **The chemical value chain may be “de-fossilized”, but cannot be “de-carbonized”**
- ⇒ **Carbon resources will be abundantly available also in post-fossil energy scenarios, but sources are distributed and diverse**
- ⇒ **“Harvesting” renewable energy in chemicals and fuels requires fundamental research and innovation in catalysis**

“Power-to-Liquid”

F. Fischer

H. Tropsch

Gründerpreis 2018

INERATEC; Karlsruhe, Germany
Decentralized module

<http://ineratec.de>

Nordic Blue Crude

Nordic Blue; Herøya, Norway
from 2020: 10 Mio L a⁻¹

<http://nordicbluecrude.no>

Oryx; Qatar
since 2006: 1800 Mio L a⁻¹

<https://www.oryxgtl.com.qa>

„Power-to-Methanol“

Carbon2Chem
ThyssenKrupp Stahlwerk Duisburg
2020, 27 t a⁻¹

Carbon Recycling International
Stravensgj, Island, since 2016, 4 kt a⁻¹
China: 2021, 100 kt a⁻¹

Lurgi MegaMethanol Technology
1 MT a⁻¹

Green Chemistry with CO₂/H₂

„Power-To-X:“ CO₂ Enables Sector Coupling

KOPERNIKUS
P2X **PROJEKTE**
Die Zukunft unserer Energie

 Carbon4PUR

 Bundesministerium
für Bildung
und Forschung

Zivilgesellschaftlicher
Beirat

Bund für
Umwelt und
Naturschutz
Deutschland

VCI

To note: this is the SUN
Sol Iustitia Illustra Nos

SUNRISE review – framing thoughts

Prof. dr. Gert Jan Kramer
10 October 2019

The Big Picture (i)

The Big Picture (i)

Clean Tech is a 300 billion \$ industry

SUNRISE Roadmap, p. 7:

"Technologies for the transition to a low-emission society are not available on a large scale today."

That's not true

\$bn

The Choice on Carbon Management and Future Fuels

The competitive landscape of 'solar fuels'

The benchmark

Synthetic Solar Fuels: back-of-the-envelope cost

200 \$/barrel – affordable?

My Bottom-line Questions to SUNRISE

Will you be developing a new technology 'platform'?
Or will you be feeding into existing technology platforms?

I think it is (and should be) often the latter, but the roadmap seems to be written as if it is the former.

(Clarity on this is critical when shaping the consortium.)

The notable exception is Direct Atmospheric CO₂ Capture & Conversion (DACC).

(A TRL jump from 1-2 to 5-7 in 10 years seems unrealistic)

How do you plan to handle within one Programme technology development at such different TRL levels?

What synergies do you see?

UCL

Université
catholique
de Louvain

SUNRISE

Solar energy for a circular economy
Technological Roadmap

Draft

Carina Faber | Université Catholique de Louvain, Belgium
carina.faber@uclouvain.be

Context: What does the world look like today?

- A roadmap is **not an abstract object** standing on its own: its purpose comes with its **actual implementation and the solution it brings to real-world challenges**
- It is crucial to **analyze the specific context** in which it will have to persist;
- Even though it is a **technology roadmap, strongly dependent on non-technological enablers such as financing mechanisms, political support and social commitment**
- Some of the trends will accelerate the development of the proposed solar-driven SUNRISE technologies, others will hamper them.
- The latter have to be anticipated and, if possible, circumvented.

HIGHER TEMPERATURES

EXTENDED PERIODS OF DROUGHT

INCREASED RISK OF WILDFIRE

INTENSE RAIN AND FLOODING

HIGHER ENERGY COSTS

Context: What does the world look like today?

What are today's drivers? And Challenges?

Ecological drivers

- Today's **energy production system strongly depends on fossil-based energy sources and raw materials**
- Their intensive use over the last decades not only depleted the Earth's reservoirs, but also caused a **significant increase of the carbon dioxide concentration** in the atmosphere
- Latest reports point out the **tremendous consequences** of the ongoing warming on ecosystems, resources and accordingly society in general
- In EU, **energy and transport sectors** generate the major part of GHG emissions (54% and 24% in 2016)
- **Chemical industry**, one of the largest industrial GHG emitters in Europe

Already in 2050, burning of fossil fuels should no longer be the rule but the exception in technologically well-developed countries

Technologies for the transition to a low-emission society not available on a large-scale today.

Scenarios: What will the world look like in 2050?

Scenarios: What will the world look like in 2050?

- SUNRISE envisions the **sustainable production of chemicals and fuels using solar energy and raw materials abundantly available in the atmosphere**
- Due to high number of considered products (ranging from hydrogen to jet fuel) and broad scope of proposed technologies with different degrees of maturity, **beyond the scope of this roadmap to model future scenarios based on current data**
- Future needs of chemicals and fuels estimated by analyzing different scenarios described in the current literature:
 - **“2050 long-term strategy climate-neutral Europe” (EC 2018)**
 - **Recent reports of the International Panel on Climate Change**

These scenarios set frame for the goals to be achieved by the proposed technologies.

Scenarios: What will the world look like in 2050?

2050 long-term strategy climate-neutral Europe

- confirms Europe's commitment as a leader in global climate action
- presents a vision for **achieving net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050**
- **socially fair transition**
- **Decoupling economic growth from depletion of natural resources**
- Eight economy-wide scenarios, divided in three different categories depending on their levels of emission reductions (from 80% to 100%)
- The scenarios cover the potential range of required reductions for the EU to contribute its share to the Paris Agreement's temperature objectives ("*well below 2°C*" and "*1.5°C temperature change*").

IPCC Special Report Global Warming of 1.5°C

- discusses impacts of global warming of 1.5 °C above pre-industrial levels and four illustrative global model greenhouse gas emission pathways
- In pathways for limiting global warming to 1.5°C, CO₂ emissions are reduced globally to net zero around 2050
- All pathways examined use Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR), but in different amounts

Scenarios: What will the world look like in 2050?

Implications for SUNRISE

- **energy system transition is underway**
- highest ambition level can only be achieved if all mitigation options are exploited: **electrification, hydrogen, bio-based feedstocks and substitution**
- **SUNRISE technologies with low technological readiness are not included** in the described scenarios, but their great impact (projected as 2 TW for Europe alone), will determine the electricity demand and the decentralization for industry decarbonization
- some scenarios, such as the fourth illustrative pathway in the IPCC report mentioned above, **largely rely on the deployment of a BECCS model**, where biomass becomes an important energy carrier. For this pathway, the needed land area for bioenergy is expected to amount to 7.2 million km², globally, by 2050: **land use, biodiversity!**

The development of technologies included in the SUNRISE portfolio alleviate the needs for land use, water and nutrients consumption, since they are based on decoupling of economic growth from depletion of resources, while high solar-to-fuel yields are targeted

Vision: How to get the future we want?

The vision of **SUNRISE** is to enable a circular economy of renewable fuels and chemicals on a global scale using abundant molecules as feedstocks (e.g. water, carbon dioxide, nitrogen) and, in the long term, sunlight as the sole energy source.

- SUNRISE wants to develop **artificial photosynthesis technologies in a broad sense**
- aiming at **solar-to-products yields tenfold to hundredfold higher than current biomass practice**
- Using the **smallest possible land area** is a key objective in order to propose technologies compatible with other essential goals (sustainable food production system, preservation of biodiversity)
- based on ubiquitous resources - thus enabling a **purely decentralized and import-independent production system**
- SUNRISE will create **substantial added value for all European countries** by providing **tailored solutions** for each European region to achieve the **best utilization of solar irradiance and site-specific resources**

WHY?

Energy security

Carbon-neutral Europe 2050

CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION
COMPETITIVE EU KEY INDUSTRIAL PILLARS

Energy resilience

Import-independent production

EU RESILIENCE

Socially-fair transition to low-carbon society

WHAT?

Defossilization of energy sector

Defossilization of transport sector

Sustainable hydrogen

Long-term: Reduction of atmospheric CO2

Defossilization of chemical industry

Decentralized production based on local resources

Large-scale deployment of negative-emission technologies

CO2 as valuable feedstock

Sustainable fuels and chemicals

Long-lasting carbon materials

Sustainable ammonia

HOW?

Electro-chemical conversion

Direct solar conversion

Direct bio(hybrid) conversion

Vision: How to get the future we want?

The **sustainable large-scale production of solar fuels and chemicals** is key to enable the SUNRISE vision. It is based on both **point and distributed sources of carbon dioxide**, the **ultimate goal being the extraction of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and its long-term storage in long-lasting carbon materials**.

- Given the vast variety of possible solar fuels and chemicals, SUNRISE has to limit its efforts to special classes of products to **ensure efficiency of a joint large-scale research effort**
- **fuels and chemical commodities**, which are needed and produced in **large volumes** today (millions of tons per year or more on a global scale) and sold at a **small price** (range of 1€ per liter)
- market is a major **challenge, calling for very efficient, simplified and durable processes**
- Ubiquitous low-energy species extracted from environment and upgraded with abundant renewables
- High-value molecules (e.g. pharmaceuticals) are low volume markets; exception: fuels, fatty acids, biodegradable plastics

Key molecules considered in SUNRISE are highlighted in the yellow oval area, comprising fuels and chemical commodities, but not high-value molecules per se.

© Hervé Bercegol (CEA)

The **SUNRISE** roadmap is structured around the products we can provide to society, not the technologies.

Vision: How to get the future we want?

Example: Hydrogen

- highly important energy vector
- Especially wrt transport sector, already well-covered topic: existing European large-scale structures such as the **private public partnership *Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking (FCH JU)*** and their recently released *Hydrogen Europe Roadmap*
- **Sustainable, large-scale hydrogen production is central to the SUNRISE vision**
- Hydrogen represents an **enabling molecule** in the production of ammonia and carbon-based fuels and chemicals
- not only electricity-based hydrogen technologies with a high technology-readiness-level (TRL) are considered; less mature methods based on the direct conversion of sunlight to hydrogen have a prominent place
- **A significant increase of the solar-to-hydrogen yield, high demands on sustainability and circularity in the systems and an economically-viable production of solar hydrogen are key drivers.**

SUNRISE Roadmap: how to go from the current state to the vision?

SUNRISE Roadmap: how to go from the current state to the vision?

SUNRISE: Solar energy for a circular economy

Vision

The sustainable production of fuels and commodity chemicals at affordable costs of materials and Earth surface using solar energy

Three main technological approaches

- mimick natural photosynthesis to **store solar energy** in chemical compounds
- energy from light, water and carbon dioxide transformed into **solar fuels** (hydrogen and carbon-based fuels)
- multitude of different technologies, three main areas:
solar-driven electrochemical conversion, photo(electro)chemical and biological/bio-hybrid approaches

SUNRISE Roadmap: how to go from the current state to the vision?

© Carina Faber, UCLouvain

Electrochemical conversion with solar power

Direct conversion via photo(electro)chemical systems

combine everything necessary to go directly from sunlight to the final chemical product

includes biomolecular systems: biological molecules extracted from living cells wired to inorganic components

© Carina Faber, UCLouvain

© Carina Faber, UCLouvain

Direct conversion via photo(electro)chemical systems

living photosynthetic cell factories
includes biohybrid systems: living microbes wired to inorganic components

SUNRISE Roadmap: how to go from the current state to the vision?

Technological milestones to be achieved

- Carbon, hydrogen, oxygen and nitrogen are the main atomic building blocks
- Molecular hydrogen, H_2 are key in the reduction of carbon dioxide and nitrogen

SUNRISE Roadmap: how to go from the current state to the vision?

Sustainable Hydrogen production

The SUNRISE vision is to produce green hydrogen in a fully sustainable way, exclusively using solar energy and abundantly available materials and resources

SUNRISE Roadmap: how to go from the current state to the vision?

Major milestones

SUNRISE Roadmap: how to go from the current state to the vision?

Major technological targets

SUNRISE key enabling technologies

The future deployment of SUNRISE technologies at scale, providing net global GHG reductions, necessitates enabling resources, technologies and analyses.

Upscaling, i.e. bringing novel technological solutions from the lab to a global industrial scale, is a significant challenge for mature SUNRISE technologies. The overall sustainability, the availability of needed resources on a large scale and economic viability have to be ensured.

Novel materials will allow cost-competitive, efficient and durable solutions across the three proposed technological SUNRISE approaches.

Product separation, i.e. the conversion of a mixture of chemical substances into distinct products, is a crucial step once the desired solar fuel or chemical is produced by the artificial photosynthesis device; in most of today's devices product separation, purification and collection represent one of the major bottlenecks due to the energy consumed for production and operation.

The SUNRISE tool-box comprises **computational materials modelling, quantitative sustainability assessment, synthetic biology and emerging concepts.**

Needed resources beyond the scope of SUNRISE

Social and environmental impact

Land use and freshwater demand

The deployment of any new technology should carefully consider the additional land use and freshwater demands in this context.

Impact of SUNRISE technology on the environmental resources

	Today global production ^a [Mt / y]	Production potential ^b [tons ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹]	Land use [km ²]	Freshwater use ^c [Mt / y]
Hydrogen	70	52 - 130	13 500 - 5 400	630
Formic Acid	< 1	1 182 - 2 956	8 - 3	< 0.5
Formaldehyde	52	386 - 964	1 350 - 540	30
Methanol	75	274 - 686	2 700 - 1 100	85
Ethanol	95	197 - 494	4 800 - 1 900	110
Ammonia	176	308 - 772	5 700 - 2 300	280

Technical Appendix: technologies and milestones

on the “call level” of future work programmes

Sustainable hydrogen production

1. Large-Scale hydrogen production using PEM electrolysis
 2. Hydrogen-production using photoelectrochemical cell devices
- ...

Sustainable ammonia production

1. Renewable Haber-Bosch process
 2. Electrochemical ammonia synthesis
- ...

Sustainable carbon-based chemicals and (jet)fuel production

1. Dark electrochemical reduction of CO₂ to C₁/C₂/C₃ products
 2. Electrochemical production of hydrocarbon fuels
- ...

Carbon capture technologies

1. Amine-based carbon capture
 2. Low-Temperature Direct Air Capture
- ...

Enabling technologies

...

A great team work with excellent researchers from all-over Europe:

Yagut Allahverdiyeva-Rinne (University of Turku), Vincent Artero (CEA), Laurent Baraton (Engie), Andrea Barbieri (CNR), Hervé Bercegol (CEA), Maximilian Fleischer (Siemens), Han Huynhthi (Engie), Joanna Kargul (Warsaw University), Hélène Lepaumier (Engie), Laura Lopez (ICIQ), Ann Magnuson (Uppsala University), Arne Roth (Fraunhofer)

SUNRISE Roadmap: Next steps

A roadmap takes its only purpose from being implemented!

Content:

- **revise milestones, extend technical appendix forms, etc.**
 - **this afternoon: split into discussion groups (H2, NH3, carbon-based fuels, technical appendix)**
- **extend to international level (tomorrow)**

Lobbying:

- **decide for publication state**
- **disseminate draft roadmap to national and European contacts, colleagues**
- **present roadmap to EC (e.g. lunchtime meeting DG energy)**
 - **this afternoon: group discussing about possible strategies**

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Recommendations

- Couple to use/cleaning of less-clean water? (connect to SDG "clean water")
- State that this is a tech development, not a business case development map (we don't point out where businesses can be made).
- Point out knowledge transfer between the different approaches and targets (e.g. H₂ vs CO₂)
- Explain how targets on efficiency and scale have been set.
- IPCEI on Hydrogen. Check their goals for large scale projects (100 MW to several GW before 2028).
- Write that SUNRISE will analyse all technologies with respect to scalability, sustainability, environmental footprint.

Add to the schemes goals in terms of scalability and sustainability (replace IrOx with earth abundant, etc.).

- P 31: 4 Euro/kg in 2025 is probably too high (Milestone in Scheme).
- P31 should not goals rather be "X% of EU fuel provided by solar H₂", that specifying the size of one plant?
- P31 it looks like PEC can never be large scale, but only decentralized – is this intentional?
- References to how projected costs have been calculated.
- Note on the use of units (kg⁻¹, kWh⁻¹ etc.) + how STH efficiencies were calculated.
- P. 32 add to key enabling technologies: "cat + membranes that can operate at different conditions (pH, waste water...)"
- Are "visions for 2050" aligned with those from the vision document – check!
- P. 34: The scheme looks wrong. "Now" looks like "Goals", while >1 year stability may be 2025-2030, but finally must be >10 years

Recommendations

- P 21 Clarify that it is production of H₂ is the focus.
- Couple to use/cleaning of less-clean water? (connect to SDG "clean water")
- References to how projected costs have been calculated.
- Note on the use of units (kg⁻¹, kWh⁻¹ etc.) + how STH efficiencies were calculated.
- State that this is a tech development, not a business case development map. (we don't point out where businesses can be made).
- Point out knowledge transfer between the different approaches and targets (e.g. H₂ vs CO₂)
- Explain how targets on efficiency and scale have been set.
- IPCEI on Hydrogen. Check their goals for large scale projects (100 MW to several GW before 2028).
- Write that SUNRISE will analyse all technologies with respect to scalability, sustainability, environmental footprint.
- P 31 ff: add to the schemes goals in terms of scalability and sustainability (replace IrOx with earth abundant, etc.)
- P 31: 4 Euro/kg in 2025 is probably too high (Milestone in Scheme). The cost estimates in the text below lack references.
- P. 31: clarify in the text that the milestone 2025 is not just for SOE. In addition, ion exchange electrolyzers should be mentioned ("ENAPTER" – company that started).
- P31 should not goals rather be "X% of EU fuel provided by solar H₂", that specifying the size of one plant?
- P31 it looks like PEC can never be large scale, but only decentralized – is this intentional?

Moderator: **MI IC5/ Sunrise roadmapping workshop : Break-out session Ammonia**

Vincent Artero (CEA)

Participants:

Roel van de Krol (HZB)

Tony Vlcek (Heyrovsky Institute)

Rita Toth (EMPA)

Medhi Jafarian (Univ Adelaide)

Recommendations:

1. Consider NH_3 as a energy (H_2) carrier/fuels? (add a arrow to fuels and electricity in scheme page 29)
2. Concerns about safety?
3. Photocatalytic N_2 fixation (including molecular systems) should be included, with same caution as for electrocatalytic systems. Relevant in the N_2 + water production scheme (right on the scheme p 37)
4. Introduce explicitly SOE for NH_3 production (<https://arpa-e.energy.gov/?q=slick-sheet-project/solid-state-alkaline-electrolyzer-ammonia-synthesis>).
5. The sentence « catalysis research with ab-initio modelling and high-throughput screening, in-operando analytical tools, multi-scale modelling, systems engineering, life-cycle cost Analysis » is also valid for electro and photo(electro)chemical N_2 fixation
6. N_2 capture, concentration and separation from O_2 in matrices deposited on (photo)electrodes or photocatalysts.
7. Develop biohybrid systems (see Nocera PNAS 2017)
8. Life-cycle & environmental footprint (indicated in the enabler box) should be developed in the text

Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

- A Coordination and Support Action (CSA) -

Meeting between **SUNRISE** and **Mission Innovation IC5**

Breakout session : Carbon-based molecules

James, Arne, Helene, Herve, Huub, Julio, Nicola, Thomas, Winfried

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 816336

10 recommendations

1. Bioeconomy should be mentioned
 - a) Synergies on CO₂ reduction.
 - b) Link with 200 platform chemicals of biomass (photo)conversion
 - c) Mention existing pathways of production
2. Express goals in units understandable by policy makers, and adapted to the chemical industry (compared to volume of chemical products)
 - a) Products not specified
 - b) Find data
3. Why not limit to H₂ + thermochemical processes ?
 - a) Like Dan Nocera suggested to us in June
 - b) Present TRL= 6 (not 4, correction needed).
 - c) Include solar thermochemical as solar-assisted thermochemical conversion.
 - d) Also addition of H₂ (from renewables) to improve thermochemical system.
 - e) Put this story first, before electroreduction of CO₂
4. Justification of CO₂ electroreduction vs High Temp steps could be improved and detailed
 - a) Selectivity, not well defined, not enough focused onto.
5. Advantages and disadvantages of high or low current densities : avoid contradiction and paradoxes
 - a. Relate electroreduction of CO₂ to concentrated sources;

6. Energy-efficiency of product purification
7. Need of a section on catalysis: there we need energy-X.
 - a) Low current density catalysis. Catalysis for PEC should be highlighted in the main document (supposing it is enough described in the Appendix).
8. PEC for CO₂
 - a) TRL = 1-3 (NOT 3-4)
 - b) Decentralized AND CO are not compatible. Focus on a realistic product for decentralized deployment (= at the level of users)
 - c) Blue graphic on p. 51 should have more technical details
9. biocatalytic
 - a) “Novel strategies to avoid contaminations of production cells from foreign strains” should be solved before pilot stage (by 2025)
10. Availability of CO₂ questionable – even though abundance is certain
 - a) What is the thermodynamic limit of CO₂ capture?
 - b) System thinking, as in section 10 of Energy-X Research Needs

Thank You

"The world has enough for everyone's need... but not enough for everyone's greed."

Mahatma Gandhi

- Suggestions for contents, context, scenarios, vision
- Suggestions for impact towards the community, EC and members states (Lobbying)
- Members of the group:
- Joanna Kargul, Yagut Allahverdiyeva, Amelia Ochoa, Stefan Baumann, Laura Lopez, Philippe Schild, Carina Faber, Frédéric Chandezon (moderator)

- The roadmapping team should reconsider the thermochemical processes to be integrated (or not) in the roadmap and/or a how document
 - Stefan leader
- Context:
 - Add footnotes for clarification for energy consumption
 - Specify in the introduction that we analyzed scenarios and not made ours

- Get official version of the roadmap ready with green light of the SUNRISE management board to disseminate it
- Making awareness of this roadmap at different levels: community (to strengthen it), the MS, EC and beyond

- Inform via the newsletter the supporters that the roadmap is available and what feedback is expected from them
 - Roadmap is available for download on web page
 - Technical appendix downloadable (\approx 170 pages) and is splitted in sections so that supporters can download the section they are most interested in
 - Feedback needed not on the wording but on the how documents: specifications, milestones, mapping the gaps in the how documents (mapping and gapping

- Public dissemination of the roadmap (executive summary) in national roadmap dedicated events
- Organize ASAP roadmap-events targetting high level, policy makers, representatives of industry and national funding agencies, media
 - Coordinated meetings with a standardized communication material (presentation)
 - SUNRISE national nodes should convey the message at those events

Remark: a roadmap event is not a “standard” stakeholder workshop

Remark: we are not yet that visible at the european level !

- Executive summary of the roadmap can be distributed by the commission
- Roadmap events lunches with representatives of different DGs (separate events à priori)

- Mission innovation is the right frame for that !
- An alternative is to make contact with IC via colleagues from SUNRISE and ENERGY-X having contacts

Be a change maker & Join our community!

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